

Isolation and Characterisation of a New Anthraquinone Derivative from *Cassia grandis* Linn.

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Earlier communications on various parts of *Cassia grandis*¹ showed the presence of compounds like polysaccharides, flavonoids, anthraquinonoids and their glycosides. In continuation of our studies on the phytochemical investigation of *C. grandis*, we now report the isolation of a new anthraquinone derivative from the root-bark of the plant.

Results and Discussion

The ethyl acetate extract of air-dried crushed root-bark of *C. grandis* on column chromatography afforded a compound. Formation of red colour with methanolic sodium hydroxide and also with methanolic magnesium acetate indicated the compound to be an anthraquinone. The compound formed a monoacetate showing the presence of one hydroxyl group. It was found to have two methoxyl groups² (Zeisel; 2 940 cm⁻¹). The ethanolic solution of the compound formed a complex with ethanolic copper sulphate showing the presence of the hydroxyl function in α -position to the C=O function³. The presence of the α -hydroxyl group is also supported by ν_{\max} at 1 630 and 1 665 cm⁻¹ and λ_{\max} at 405 nm. The ir peak at 2 898 cm⁻¹ suggests the presence of C-methyl group. The compound gave red colour on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid, showing the presence of at least one methoxyl group in any α -position⁴. The compound on oxidation gave 3,5-dimethoxyphthalic acid (m.p. and m.m.p. 155–56°, co-tlc) as one of the oxidation products which places the two methoxyl groups in positions either 6 and 8, or 5 and 7 with respect to α -OH group. The demethylated compound (HI-P) gave all the positive tests for 1,8-dihydroxy system⁵ showing the presence of two methoxyl groups at C-6 and C-8 respectively. ¹H nmr spectrum shows signals corresponding to two similarly located C-methyl groups at δ 2.40 (6H, s), these being present at β -positions; two methoxyl groups at δ 3.90 (3H, s) and 3.98 (3H, s) and one chelated hydroxyl at 12.06 (1H, s). The presence of three aromatic protons (two of them *meta*-coupled) is shown by the signals at δ 6.86 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 7.74 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz) and 7.97 (1H, s). In its mass spectrum the fragment ions at *m/z* 149 and 121 also suggest the location of the two methyl groups on the aromatic ring carrying one hydroxyl group. Fragment ions at *m/z* 165 and 137 suggest that the other aromatic ring of the compound has two methoxyl groups.

The foregoing observation establishes the structure of the new anthraquinone derivative as 1-hydroxy-6,8-dimethoxy-2,3-dimethyl-9,10-anthraquinone.

Experimental

Anthraquinone derivative : The air-dried crushed pieces of root-bark of *C. grandis* were exhaustively extracted in a soxhlet using petroleum ether, benzene and ethyl acetate in succession. Bright orange-yellow crystals were isolated from ethyl acetate extract by column chromatography over silica gel column using benzene-ethyl acetate (5 : 5, v/v) as eluant, m.p. 260–62° (Found : C, 69.18; H, 5.20; OMe, 19.90. C₁₈H₁₆O₅ requires : C, 69.23; H, 5.16; OMe, 19.87%); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 226, 278 and 405 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 300, 2 940, 2 898, 1 760, 1 665, 1 630, 1 180, 735–720 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) 2.40 (6H, s, C-2 and C-3, 2×CH₃) 3.90 and 3.98 (6H, each s, C-6 and C-8, 2×OMe), 6.86 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-7), 7.74 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-5), 7.97 (1H, s, H-4) and 12.06 (1H, s, C-1, OH); *m/z* 312 [M]⁺, 294, 284, 283, 256, 165, 149, 137 and 121.

Acetyl derivative : The anthraquinone derivative was acetylated with boiling Ac₂O and pyridine to give the monoacetate, C₂₀H₁₈O₆, m.p. 232–34° (Found : acetyl, 16.62. C₂₀H₁₈O₆ requires : acetyl, 16.66%).

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